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1	Aithal, P. S.	3,322	(227)	121	(1)	27 (3899)	3,323 (4051)	0 (17347)	121	(51)	27 (10627)	0 (7516)	0 (17375)					
2	Demirgüç-Kunt, Asli	11,087	(17)	95	(2)	66 (1239)	92,034 (26)	5,438 (10)	168	(22)	548 (1501)	32 (211)	13.0315 (28)					
3	McGee, Robert W.	14,030	(11)	70	(3)	32 (3258)	142,786 (14)	4,261 (16)	443	(1)	322 (3179)	10 (1162)	3.8810 (148)					
4	Beck, Thorsten	5,826	(71)	57	(4)	43 (2291)	54,966 (76)	5,808 (9)	134	(41)	410 (2338)	43 (121)	15.2307 (20)					
5	Levine, Ross E.	7,726	(41)	38	(5)	54 (1672)	84,794 (39)	8,627 (4)	144	(35)	589 (1327)	60 (58)	23.4787 (9)					
6	Kumar, P. M. S.	1,139	(1148)	36	(6)	32 (3258)	1,139 (8715)	0 (17347)	36	(774)	32 (10422)	0 (7516)	0 (17375)					
7	Kerr, William R.	1,963	(525)	35	(7)	13 (6786)	16,382 (691)	617 (365)	146	(33)	112 (7205)	4 (2582)	1.9205 (324)					
8	Hasan, Iftekhhar	5,447	(82)	34	(8)	25 (4185)	40,034 (159)	656 (342)	220	(15)	182 (5396)	3 (3131)	0.6417 (847)					
9	Subudhi, Rabi N.	553	(2712)	29	(9)	18 (5461)	608 (12386)	0 (17347)	31	(1034)	20 (10916)	0 (7516)	0 (17375)					
10	Choi, Hak	2,100	(468)	27	(10)	9 (8131)	9,284 (1418)	114 (1801)	246	(6)	38 (10148)	0 (7516)	0.0016 (13914)					
11	Fecht, Falko	768	(1880)	26	(11)	14 (6470)	3,738 (3648)	47 (3222)	53	(351)	71 (8653)	1 (5194)	0.1502 (2355)					
12	Hoffman, Andrew J.	1,247	(1028)	23	(12)	30 (3481)	7,289 (1892)	33 (4023)	42	(566)	174 (5560)	1 (5194)	0.0977 (3082)					
12	Munshi, Jamal	7,010	(49)	23	(12)	117 (452)	16,197 (703)	0 (17347)	60	(259)	270 (3831)	0 (7516)	0 (17375)					
14	Lowry, Paul B.	5,203	(89)	22	(14)	35 (2932)	20,007 (517)	96 (2046)	148	(31)	135 (6547)	1 (5194)	0.2797 (1602)					
14	Cumming, Douglas J.	9,251	(26)	22	(14)	38 (2653)	90,754 (28)	1,457 (109)	246	(6)	369 (2692)	6 (1875)	1.7281 (357)					
16	Ji, Qiang	298	(4923)	21	(16)	14 (6470)	298 (17373)	0 (17347)	21	(1960)	14 (11124)	0 (7516)	0.0042 (11507)					
16	Maksimovic, Vojislav	1,702	(652)	21	(16)	35 (2932)	24,311 (390)	1,879 (79)	49	(411)	496 (1773)	38 (157)	3.7714 (157)					
16	Bogensneider, Bret N.	2,143	(454)	21	(16)	63 (1331)	2,626 (4882)	0 (17347)	34	(862)	77 (8404)	0 (7516)	0 (17375)					
19	Tan, Yong	2,590	(341)	20	(19)	58 (1504)	9,431 (1393)	22 (5026)	45	(492)	210 (4836)	0 (7516)	0.0199 (6909)					

20	Perić, Goran	194	(6973)	18	(20)	10	(7787)	205	(19967)	0	(17347)	19	(2295)	11	(11210)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
20	Williams, Colin C.	1,999	(509)	18	(20)	9	(8131)	4,818	(2859)	136	(1571)	223	(13)	22	(10830)	1	(5194)	0.6526	(835)
22	Gertler, Paul J.	766	(1888)	17	(22)	14	(6470)	5,984	(2323)	262	(875)	53	(351)	113	(7186)	5	(2194)	0.5543	(939)
23	Eskeland, Gunnar S.	263	(5452)	16	(23)	11	(7420)	2,923	(4514)	154	(1413)	24	(1578)	122	(6908)	6	(1875)	0.3337	(1401)
23	Pirson, Michael	4,081	(152)	16	(23)	49	(1941)	17,105	(653)	50	(3113)	83	(120)	206	(4920)	1	(5194)	0.0430	(4842)
23	Agarwal, Sumit	6,126	(63)	16	(23)	42	(2359)	39,675	(164)	414	(574)	146	(33)	272	(3802)	3	(3131)	1.1778	(507)
23	Pradhan, Radhe Shyam	1,472	(817)	16	(23)	77	(968)	3,131	(4241)	2	(12544)	19	(2295)	165	(5752)	0	(7516)	0.0016	(13914)
23	Van Reenen, John M.	2,215	(432)	16	(23)	18	(5461)	12,278	(1016)	1,338	(124)	122	(49)	101	(7566)	11	(1043)	4.4240	(128)
23	Friedman, Hershey H.	7,425	(43)	16	(23)	50	(1872)	31,087	(261)	33	(4023)	149	(30)	209	(4851)	0	(7516)	0.3444	(1364)
23	Cadot, Olivier	95	(11363)	16	(23)	2	(10933)	1,445	(7526)	131	(1615)	45	(492)	32	(10422)	3	(3131)	0.1250	(2668)
30	Jedidi, Kamel	189	(7130)	15	(30)	9	(8131)	1,272	(8171)	5	(9658)	20	(2132)	64	(8938)	0	(7516)	0.1610	(2255)
30	Gasic, Marko	163	(7945)	15	(30)	10	(7787)	174	(21125)	0	(17347)	16	(2959)	11	(11210)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
30	Klein, Michael U.	642	(2302)	15	(30)	36	(2845)	6,433	(2153)	63	(2735)	18	(2501)	357	(2804)	4	(2582)	0.1979	(1994)
30	Xekalaki, Evdokia	252	(5666)	15	(30)	4	(10261)	3,748	(3640)	48	(3181)	66	(209)	57	(9236)	1	(5194)	0.2624	(1671)
30	Aithal, Shubhrajyotsna	444	(3431)	15	(30)	30	(3481)	444	(14461)	0	(17347)	15	(3213)	30	(10506)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
30	Ayyagari, Meghana	1,026	(1307)	15	(30)	41	(2426)	10,869	(1179)	163	(1345)	25	(1482)	435	(2145)	7	(1659)	0.1928	(2021)
36	Parsons, Christopher Robert	376	(3995)	14	(36)	21	(4835)	1,279	(8146)	26	(4588)	18	(2501)	71	(8653)	1	(5194)	0.0196	(6944)
36	Clarke, George	512	(2950)	14	(36)	13	(6786)	11,089	(1151)	592	(386)	39	(657)	284	(3619)	15	(737)	0.6398	(850)
36	Wei, Shang-Jin	1,504	(792)	14	(36)	8	(8535)	18,568	(579)	2,920	(35)	190	(18)	98	(7668)	15	(737)	11.5140	(34)
36	Caporale, Guglielmo Maria	1,162	(1111)	14	(36)	11	(7420)	8,651	(1536)	88	(2195)	108	(63)	80	(8286)	1	(5194)	0.0656	(3900)
36	van Ours, Jan C.	1,071	(1245)	14	(36)	5	(9839)	10,997	(1161)	746	(294)	237	(9)	46	(9750)	3	(3131)	1.7206	(360)
36	Paseda, Oluseun A.	288	(5066)	14	(36)	21	(4835)	288	(17580)	0	(17347)	14	(3524)	21	(10878)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
36	Nault, Barrie R.	247	(5764)	14	(36)	5	(9839)	2,344	(5324)	87	(2214)	48	(430)	49	(9607)	2	(3922)	0.1848	(2084)
36	Weber, Michael	1,689	(657)	14	(36)	60	(1428)	3,468	(3909)	6	(9060)	28	(1220)	124	(6855)	0	(7516)	0.0133	(8118)
36	Vuong, Quan Hoang	824	(1732)	14	(36)	14	(6470)	8,495	(1565)	104	(1927)	61	(245)	139	(6438)	2	(3922)	0.1911	(2031)
36	Calomiris, Charles W.	2,004	(507)	14	(36)	21	(4835)	12,597	(986)	790	(269)	96	(82)	131	(6665)	8	(1469)	2.4941	(246)
46	Shenoy, Varun	268	(5377)	13	(46)	21	(4835)	268	(18086)	0	(17347)	13	(3858)	21	(10878)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
46	Madan, Dilip B.	2,299	(404)	13	(46)	21	(4835)	29,172	(290)	977	(209)	107	(66)	273	(3785)	9	(1300)	1.2290	(496)
46	Madhani, Pankaj M.	3,728	(178)	13	(46)	30	(3481)	23,688	(403)	25	(4683)	125	(47)	190	(5223)	0	(7516)	0.0011	(14697)
46	Massa, Massimo	3,054	(253)	13	(46)	22	(4655)	48,399	(107)	914	(230)	136	(40)	356	(2816)	7	(1659)	2.5220	(239)
46	Murad, Md. W.	104	(10727)	13	(46)	7	(8953)	268	(18086)	0	(17347)	16	(2959)	17	(11020)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
46	Zhang, Anming	692	(2104)	13	(46)	20	(5031)	1,561	(7146)	16	(5921)	34	(862)	46	(9750)	0	(7516)	0.0183	(7144)
46	Hong, Yili	2,645	(329)	13	(46)	71	(1101)	5,740	(2417)	4	(10424)	37	(732)	155	(5994)	0	(7516)	0.0015	(14051)
46	Harvey, Campbell R.	30,858	(3)	13	(46)	180	(161)	253,014	(6)	7,885	(5)	171	(19)	1,480	(170)	46	(107)	25.5671	(4)
46	Kumar, Alok	5,672	(77)	13	(46)	77	(968)	53,498	(82)	789	(271)	74	(164)	723	(901)	11	(1043)	2.1950	(289)
46	Mitchell, Olivia S.	3,149	(242)	13	(46)	13	(6786)	28,176	(313)	1,984	(74)	244	(8)	115	(7142)	8	(1469)	10.1863	(54)
46	Stulz, René M.	8,412	(35)	13	(46)	39	(2562)	131,674	(16)	7,364	(6)	218	(16)	604	(1268)	34	(182)	20.0746	(14)
46	Larcker, David F.	11,944	(14)	13	(46)	116	(461)	108,819	(21)	1,355	(120)	103	(74)	1,056	(384)	13	(876)	1.9287	(322)
46	Lucey, Brian M.	4,419	(117)	13	(46)	31	(3357)	48,157	(109)	154	(1413)	141	(36)	342	(2978)	1	(5194)	0.1871	(2069)
46	Afonso, Antonio	1,653	(680)	13	(46)	12	(7086)	16,956	(661)	582	(398)	140	(38)	121	(6938)	4	(2582)	0.4805	(1050)
46	Cheung, Yin-Wong	1,134	(1159)	13	(46)	9	(8131)	15,642	(738)	636	(357)	129	(42)	121	(6938)	5	(2194)	1.7521	(351)
46	Tiongson, Erwin R.	400	(3763)	13	(46)	12	(7086)	4,377	(3145)	158	(1384)	33	(912)	133	(6613)	5	(2194)	0.1801	(2120)
46	Adeney, Elizabeth	120	(9806)	13	(46)	9	(8131)	120	(23636)	0	(17347)	13	(3858)	9	(11264)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
46	Blanke, Jordan M.	249	(5723)	13	(46)	19	(5229)	249	(18603)	0	(17347)	13	(3858)	19	(10940)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)

46	Lin, Chen	4,363	(126)	13	(46)	51	(1826)	21,412	(471)	137	(1563)	85	(110)	252	(4083)	2	(3922)	0.0679	(3818)
46	Harrison, Ann E.	358	(4154)	13	(46)	8	(8535)	3,172	(4188)	892	(235)	45	(492)	70	(8699)	20	(510)	2.1896	(291)
46	Ivanov, Stanislav H.	2,934	(277)	13	(46)	33	(3149)	19,486	(536)	27	(4487)	88	(99)	221	(4627)	0	(7516)	0.1124	(2835)
67	Barrett, Jonathan M.	129	(9347)	12	(67)	11	(7420)	129	(23183)	0	(17347)	12	(4209)	11	(11210)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
67	Kashyap, Ravi	666	(2207)	12	(67)	19	(5229)	2,038	(5915)	0	(17347)	35	(816)	58	(9189)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
67	Vives, Xavier	677	(2160)	12	(67)	12	(7086)	3,714	(3676)	342	(680)	58	(291)	64	(8938)	6	(1875)	1.3148	(457)
67	de Haan, Jakob	2,177	(444)	12	(67)	18	(5461)	20,438	(491)	677	(329)	119	(53)	172	(5599)	6	(1875)	0.6691	(815)
67	Stiglitz, Joseph E.	2,714	(314)	12	(67)	17	(5701)	19,627	(529)	1,512	(107)	159	(25)	123	(6888)	10	(1162)	12.4115	(29)
67	Gurova, Irina M.	54	(15351)	12	(67)	5	(9839)	54	(28424)	0	(17347)	12	(4209)	5	(11351)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
67	Geloso, Vincent	574	(2598)	12	(67)	36	(2845)	653	(11955)	0	(17347)	16	(2959)	41	(9998)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
67	Chohan, Usman W.	1,116	(1182)	12	(67)	70	(1132)	1,156	(8639)	0	(17347)	16	(2959)	72	(8617)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
67	Salter, Alexander W.	1,665	(670)	12	(67)	32	(3258)	5,126	(2698)	1	(14325)	52	(363)	99	(7644)	0	(7516)	0.0022	(13240)
67	De Weerd, Joachim	201	(6800)	12	(67)	10	(7787)	902	(10009)	29	(4323)	20	(2132)	45	(9803)	1	(5194)	0.0471	(4632)
77	Cohen, Lauren	2,994	(266)	11	(77)	88	(747)	7,927	(1725)	337	(688)	34	(862)	233	(4415)	10	(1162)	0.6114	(879)
77	Tayan, Brian	6,049	(66)	11	(77)	96	(638)	29,051	(291)	10	(7397)	63	(226)	461	(1971)	0	(7516)	0.0160	(7544)
77	Williams, Julian M.	920	(1495)	11	(77)	33	(3149)	3,938	(3488)	9	(7771)	28	(1220)	141	(6391)	0	(7516)	0.0065	(10218)
77	Phillips, Peter C.	1,530	(775)	11	(77)	9	(8131)	17,053	(659)	890	(236)	171	(19)	100	(7593)	5	(2194)	2.5531	(236)
77	Bayraktar, Nihal	293	(4988)	11	(77)	17	(5701)	3,892	(3530)	53	(3031)	17	(2711)	229	(4494)	3	(3131)	0.0406	(4996)
77	Ugoani, John N.	953	(1434)	11	(77)	18	(5461)	2,885	(4560)	2	(12544)	54	(332)	53	(9430)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
77	Mahony, Chris	231	(6072)	11	(77)	21	(4835)	231	(19109)	0	(17347)	11	(4695)	21	(10878)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
77	Yoon, Yeomin	508	(2979)	11	(77)	19	(5229)	6,453	(2148)	5	(9658)	27	(1300)	239	(4307)	0	(7516)	0.0129	(8214)
77	Acharya, Sridhar	182	(7330)	11	(77)	17	(5701)	182	(20816)	0	(17347)	11	(4695)	17	(11020)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
77	Gehman, Joel	1,109	(1189)	11	(77)	41	(2426)	4,757	(2894)	6	(9060)	27	(1300)	176	(5516)	0	(7516)	0.0046	(11231)
87	Wan, Xiang	208	(6614)	10	(87)	21	(4835)	208	(19856)	0	(17347)	10	(5235)	21	(10878)	0	(7516)	0.0009	(15001)
87	Krishna Prasad, K.	214	(6460)	10	(87)	21	(4835)	214	(19663)	0	(17347)	10	(5235)	21	(10878)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
87	Durand, Rodolphe	698	(2089)	10	(87)	23	(4499)	2,518	(5058)	34	(3948)	30	(1086)	84	(8133)	1	(5194)	0.0712	(3716)
87	Giroud, Xavier	625	(2385)	10	(87)	19	(5229)	7,520	(1831)	146	(1492)	33	(912)	228	(4515)	4	(2582)	0.4464	(1119)
87	Argandoña, Antonio	1,065	(1255)	10	(87)	22	(4655)	8,013	(1709)	27	(4487)	49	(411)	164	(5777)	1	(5194)	0.0444	(4758)
87	Mueller, Holger M.	613	(2442)	10	(87)	7	(8953)	16,060	(712)	344	(675)	88	(99)	183	(5360)	4	(2582)	1.3202	(456)
87	Kaminer, Debbie	278	(5214)	10	(87)	25	(4185)	318	(16871)	0	(17347)	11	(4695)	29	(10549)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
87	van Praag, Mirjam	1,324	(940)	10	(87)	19	(5229)	14,348	(818)	258	(887)	71	(179)	202	(4997)	4	(2582)	0.2624	(1671)
87	Nwachukwu, Jacinta C.	502	(3026)	10	(87)	17	(5701)	1,099	(8892)	2	(12544)	30	(1086)	37	(10198)	0	(7516)	0.0058	(10566)
87	Lerner, Josh	5,288	(87)	10	(87)	38	(2653)	88,067	(35)	2,911	(36)	141	(36)	625	(1197)	21	(474)	13.9219	(26)
87	Cho, Daegon	436	(3496)	10	(87)	34	(3049)	1,147	(8677)	0	(17347)	13	(3858)	88	(7987)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
87	Hull, Clyde E.	90	(11716)	10	(87)	8	(8535)	91	(25406)	0	(17347)	12	(4209)	8	(11295)	0	(7516)	0.0028	(12581)
87	M.D., Pradeep	191	(7063)	10	(87)	19	(5229)	191	(20439)	0	(17347)	10	(5235)	19	(10940)	0	(7516)	0	(17375)
87	Teece, David J.	3,081	(250)	10	(87)	83	(843)	13,544	(886)	72	(2509)	37	(732)	366	(2719)	2	(3922)	0.0988	(3063)

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